

Title: Deep-Insulation: HVAC Insulation malfunction detection through modeling & Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring

Name: Nathaniel Shimoni

Affiliation: Data Scientist @ Grid4c

INTRODUCTION:

HVACs are some of the most consuming appliances households use, yet most owners can't measure their efficiency. Grid4c's solutions introduce state of the art ML & DL based insights for various ways to increase energy efficiency.

AIM:

To detect insulation malfunction in private households without the use of dedicated sensor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

We conducted a research on some 5000 houses, over the course of 3 months period. We used convolutional neural networks alongside with classical machine learning techniques to detect houses with ongoing insulation, problems which translated to inefficient electricity consumption

RESULTS:

We were able to significantly improve our detection ability for insulation malfunction in houses without smart thermostat (15% improvement in AUC on previous SOTA).

CONCLUSIONS:

Applying SOTA deep learning and machine learning methods for classification and detection of electrical devices malfunctions using non-intrusive load monitoring has a great potential for increasing energy efficiency in households.

KEYWORDS:

NILM, energy efficiency, malfunction detection

BIOGRAPHY:

Nathaniel Shimoni holds a BA. in economics, and MBA both from BGU, He works as a research data scientist in Grid4C – an environmental startup that delivers insight to all energy value chain participants. Nathaniel is a data science evangelist & co-founder of the “deep-learning-boot-camp” an Israeli non-profit initiative that is making SOTA data science

more accessible, and donates its participation fees to ALS research. He is a Kaggle competitor and ranked 175 from over 60,000 active competitors.